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Traffic-related micro- and nanoplastics in air increase total and differential white blood cell counts in healthy young adults

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ABSTRACT

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are abundant in the environment, with traffic-related tyre-wear contributing substantially to atmospheric levels. MNPs have been detected in human tissues, however, their health effects remain poorly known. Therefore, we assessed immunological and respiratory health changes associated with short-term exposure to traffic-related MNPs in healthy, young adults.

In a semi-controlled study design, 23 healthy subjects participated in four-hour exposure sessions at three different sites: a highway, a stop-and-go high-traffic location and an urban park. Directly before and after, and the following morning, we collected venous blood samples to assess changes in total and differential white blood cell (WBC) counts. Before and directly after each visit we measured lung function and respiratory symptoms. During each exposure session, atmospheric synthetic and natural rubber particles were collected and measured using pyrolysis gas-chromatography coupled to mass-spectrometry, within particles smaller than 10 µm (PM₁₀). Additionally, traffic-related combustion and brake wear-related pollutants were measured including PM₁₀, ultrafine particles, black carbon, trace metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. Mixed model analyses were used to assess changes in WBC counts and lung function from baseline to post-exposure (pairwise differences), adjusting for time-varying and subject-dependent covariates.

We observed significant associations between an interquartile range increase in multiple tyre-wear rubber markers and a 7.1–9.3 % elevation in monocytes in blood obtained immediately after exposure. Moreover, in blood obtained the following morning, these associations not only persisted but increased for monocytes (9.3–17.7 %) and were additionally found for neutrophils (7.4–14.0 %). The associations remained consistent after adjusting for other traffic-related air pollutants. Null associations were found with lung function and symptoms.

Short-term exposure to traffic-related MNPs was associated with an increase in total and differential WBCs. Associations might be indicative of pro-inflammatory effects in healthy people, which could lead to clinically relevant responses in vulnerable populations.

1. Introduction

Plastic products are highly versatile, lightweight and relatively cheap to produce, resulting in their everyday and widespread usage.

(Amato-Lourenço et al., 2020) Once produced, plastics are constantly exposed to UV radiation, microbial degradation and mechanical abrasion. These processes result in the fragmentation of plastics into a very heterogeneous group of smaller-sized particles, called micro- and

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nanoplastics (MNPs). One of the main contributors of the emission of MNPs into the atmosphere is the wear and tear of rubber particles from the tyres of motorized vehicles (Koelmans et al., 2017; Quik, 2024). These tyre-wear particles (TWP) get mixed with other particles, such as brake wear, road pavement wear, and resuspension dust, resulting in tyre- and road-wear particles (TRWPs). Empirical studies using techniques such as pyrolysis–gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (Py-GC–MS), monitoring mass concentrations of TRWPs, observed the highest rubber exposure levels close to urban locations, with high motorized-road vehicle intensities (Din et al., 2024). Additionally, a previous study indicated that TRWPs contributed primarily to the coarse size range (Panko et al., 2019). However, exposure data with regards to TRWP concentrations is still scarce and highly heterogeneous.

Various studies have detected MNPs within almost every organ of the human body, including e.g. the lungs and in whole blood samples (Brits et al., 2024; Amato-Lourenço et al., 2021; Song et al., 2024). Nonetheless, epidemiological studies assessing potential health effects of exposure to MNPs, and more specifically TRWPs, remain limited. Recent observational studies focusing on potential health effects of exposure to MNPs included three cross-sectional, a prospective observational and retrospective cohort study (Marfella et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024; Nihart et al., 2025). In these studies, MNPs were found in e.g. brains, atherosclerotic plaques or blood of patients to be associated with various neurodegenerative or cardiovascular endpoints. Higher MNP levels in patients were indicative of an increased disease risk and various clinical endpoints, including stenosis, stroke, myocardial infarction and death from any cause. Moreover, two studies observed increased associations with various inflammatory markers (Marfella et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024). Limitations of the studies include limited adjustment for confounders, potential disease bias (reversed causality) and no adjustment for other correlated air pollutants, implying that it is uncertain that the reported associations with MNPs actually resulted from MNPs. Additionally, various lung (–derived) *in vitro* cell lines and inhalation rodent exposure studies have observed dose-dependent pro-inflammatory, cytotoxicity, and oxidative stress responses related to (traffic-related) MNP exposure (Gou et al., 2024; Ali et al., 2024; Bouredji et al., 2023; Bouredji et al., 2024). A major disadvantage of toxicological studies in general, include the usage of spherical polystyrene MNPs, limiting the translation to environmentally-relevant exposures (Ali et al., 2024).

Together, recent toxicological and epidemiological studies suggest that MNP exposure might result in inflammatory-related health effects (Ali et al., 2024). Therefore, the aim of the current paper was to assess potential immunological and respiratory health effects of short-term exposure to traffic-related MNPs within young, healthy adults.

2. Methods

2.1. Study participants and design

The study had a semi-experimental design based on previous studies, in which participants were exposed to traffic-related air pollution under real-world conditions with researcher control over exposure timing and environment, but no control over the exposure levels (Strak, 2012; Sinharay et al., 2018). We recruited 23 non-smoking, self-reported healthy young adults from Utrecht city (The Netherlands). Exposure sessions took place between August – October 2022 and May – July 2023. Further details on recruitment can be found in Supplement S1.

The volunteers were invited for three four-hour exposure sessions at three sites with varying traffic amounts and flow-dynamics. These sites included a stop-and-go busy road, a highway and a park as urban background location (Fig. S1). The sites were selected to capture contrast in atmospheric traffic-related MNP levels and limit high correlation with combustion-related pollutants, following previous study design. (Strak, 2012) There was at least one week of wash-out period between exposure sessions for each volunteer, with an average wash-out

period of 26.5 days (7–58 days). The volunteers were instructed to avoid major roads, take the same route and a similar mode of transport when traveling to the research facility. They were not informed of the measurement site beforehand. Measurement days were randomized across weekdays and sampling sites. Exposure sessions were scheduled at the same time of day (Fig. 1).

The exposure sessions started at 11.30 AM. Directly before and after, and the following morning, we collected venous blood samples to assess changes in total and differential white blood cell (WBC) counts and measured lung function and respiratory symptoms (Fig. 1). All health measurements were conducted at the IRAS research facility. Volunteers were transported back and forth to the measurement sites by car. Travel time was ~ 22, 15 and 15 min for respectively the highway, stop-and-go and park location. We monitored real-time ultrafine particle number concentrations (PNCs) inside the car during transport, to assess pre- and post-session exposure. To increase the inhaled dose and the contrast with transport and daily life exposures, the volunteers were instructed to cycle for 20 min each hour. The physical activity time was monitored using wearable smartwatches, maintaining 60–70 % of the volunteers' maximum heart rate (220 – AGE in years).

On-site air samples were collected using a PM₁₀ high-volume (HiVol) sampler, placed 2–5 m from the subjects. Two synthetic- and two natural rubber markers, and benzothiazole were measured using Py-GC–MS. Additionally, other components of traffic-related air pollutants (TRAPs) generated by either combustion or brake wear processes were monitored, including concentrations of trace elements (e.g. iron, copper), PM₁₀, PNC, black carbon (BC), absorbance, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). To maximize contrast between exposure and background MNP levels and for convenience of the volunteers, exposure sessions occurred without rain and with windspeeds below three Beaufort. The study protocol (#22/515) was approved by the local medical ethics review committee (NedMec, Utrecht, The Netherlands). Participants signed written informed consent forms.

2.2. Health assessment procedures

2.2.1. Hematology

Venous whole blood samples were obtained in 10 mL glass heparinized vacutainers (BD Biosciences, Plymouth, UK) using surgical-grade sterile stainless-steel 21G needles (Becton Dickinson and Company, USA). Samples were analyzed for total and differential WBC counts using the fully automated AQUIOUS CL® flow cytometer (Beckman Coulter Life Science, Miami, FL, USA). This included total WBCs, and subgroups granulocytes (neutrophils), lymphocytes and monocytes. More detailed procedures can be found in Supplement S2.

2.2.2. Spirometry

Spirometry measurements were performed using a Vitalograph Asma-1 spirometer (Vitalograph Inc, Lenexa, USA), recording both the Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 s (FEV1) and Peak Expiratory Flow (PEF). The device complies with the ERS/ATS performance criteria. All measurements were taken in a standing position, supervised by the same trained personnel. A minimum of three correctly performed tests were done and the highest value was automatically selected for further analysis.

2.2.3. Questionnaire

The volunteers were requested to fill out a questionnaire with various covariates (incidental events such as e.g. having a cold, passive smoking, medication use and caffeine intake) and current respiratory symptoms immediately before and after each session (Supplement S3). The symptoms included: coughing, dizziness, eye irritation, fatigue, give/cough up mucus, headache, itchy nose, runny nose, shortness of breath, sneezing, sore throat, stuffy nose, and wheezing.

Fig. 1. Graphical scheme of exposure session. Pre- and post-exposure health measurements at IRAS research facility.

2.3. Exposure assessment

2.3.1. Traffic-related micro- and nanoplastics

Exposure assessment has been previously reported in detail (Lenssen et al., 2025). Briefly, we collected on-site PM₁₀ samples using a HiVol sampler, on quartz microfiber sheets. Half of the quartz filter was analyzed for the mass of rubber markers as proxies for synthetic- and natural rubber components of traffic-related MNPs, using double-shot Py-GC-MS. As indicator compounds for styrene-butadiene rubber, we included 3-cyclohexene-1-yl benzene (SBR Dimer) and 1-phenyl-3,4-divinyl-(1R,3trans,4trans)-Cyclohexane (SBR Trimer). Natural rubber indicator compounds were D-Limonene and 2,5,6-trimethyl-1,3,6-Hepatriene (NR Dimer2). Additionally, we assessed the benzothiazole intensity levels, as it is commonly used as a vulcanization accelerator in rubber tyres and remains the only marker currently used to assess toxicity in various in vitro and in vivo assays (Zhang et al., 2018). We calculated the sum of NR D-Limonene and SBR Dimer ($\sum(\text{NR} + \text{SBR})$) using their molarity.

2.3.2. Traffic-related combustion and brake wear particles

Parts of the quartz filter were used to assess concentrations of trace metals using Inductively-Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS), including chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn) and iron (Fe). Additionally, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) were quantified using GC-MS. Furthermore, particles were collected on Teflon filters using Harvard Impactors for gravimetric PM₁₀ and reflectance measurements, as previously described (Lenssen et al., 2025). Briefly, real-time PNCs were measured using a DiscMini Diffusion Charger. BC was measured using a microAeth® MA200 or MA300 aethalometer. Hourly concentration data from ozone (O₃) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) were collected from fixed-site monitors in comparable microenvironments within Utrecht, available via the National Air Quality Monitoring Network (accessed via: <https://data.rivm.nl/data/luchtmeetnet.nl/>). Respectively the stations Kardinaal de Jongweg, Breukelen, and Griftpark were used for the stop-and-go, highway, and urban background (park) measurement sites.

2.3.3. Atmospheric pollen and weather data

Daily pollen counts for birch and grass pollen based on allergenicity were obtained from the nearest station (~50 km) at Medical Faculty of Leiden University (LUMC). They were included as an indicator variable for low versus high pollen counts, as previously described. (Froeling et al., 2024) Hourly weather data were averaged for the duration of each sampling campaign using records from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) station at the Bilt, 3–18 km from the sites.

2.4. Data analysis

Linear mixed effect models were used for approximately normally distributed WBC counts and lung function observations, taking into account the repeated measurements within subjects. We determined pairwise differences six hours and 17 h post-exposure versus baseline (Strak et al., 2012). We used binomial logistic mixed regression models to assess potential associations with a symptom score increase of at least 10 %.

Four fixed-factor covariate models were specified a priori. The

unadjusted model (1) included one air pollutant exposure and a random intercept per participant. The minimally adjusted model (2) additionally included the time-varying covariates temperature, relative humidity and pollen. In our main model (3) we moreover addressed potential time trends within the study period. We included days since the first visit of each year and an interaction term of year and the time trend variable to allow for separate trends by year. In the sensitivity analysis model (4), we incorporated subject-dependent covariates passive smoking, having a cold, medication use and a numeric variable accounting for differences between the mean heart rate measured at the different sites (with park as baseline), to account for potential influence of differences in physical activity (Fig. S2). Specifically, for lung function, the sensitivity analysis model included a binary variable accounting for the intake of caffeine in the morning, as caffeine is a known determinant of lung function (Welsh et al., 2010). Model 4 was a sensitivity analysis, as the added covariates were not expected to confound associations, as they are unlikely to plausibly affect changes between baseline and post-exposure levels.

Six out of the 192 blood collection procedures were unsuccessful and an additional eight samples contained not enough live cells for hematology analysis. Six of these missing samples were from the baseline measurements from different participants. Coefficient of variance (CV) values of total and differential WBCs for the baseline were determined. As the CV values were generally < 20 % (Table S1), we used the mean of the baseline values of the other two sites per volunteer, to estimate the missing baseline measurement. To address multiple testing arising from the use of multiple single-pollutant models, we applied false discovery rate (FDR) correction using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure, to the total and differential WBC associations. Corrections were applied separately for each outcome, across all pollutants and both timepoints, in order to control the FDR within each biological domain while allowing comparisons across exposures.

To adjust for potential co-exposure confounding, we performed two-pollutant analyses for the main model 3. We additionally conducted a LASSO regression model as an alternative to address potential high correlation (multicollinearity) issues compared to the mixed model approach. Further details can be found in Supplement S4.

Beta estimates and 95 % CIs were calculated for each exposure-outcome associations, standardized per interquartile range (IQR) increase in air pollutant exposure. Data analyses were performed using Rstudio, version 4.2.3. (2023-03-15 UCRT).

2.4.1. Role of funders

The sponsor of the study had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or in the writing of the report.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

We included 23 participants, with 14 participating between August to October 2022, and nine between May to August 2023 (Table 1). Eighteen participants visited three locations (78.3 %), five participants visited two locations, mainly the stop-and-go and park sites. Some participants reported in the questionnaire that, during the week of their visit to the measurement site, they had a cold (n = 5; 7.8 %), had taken medication different from their usual (n = 5; 7.8 %), or had been

Table 1
General characteristics sample population at baseline (t = 0).

	Unit	Median (IQR, or range min; max) or n (%)
Year included	2022	14 (60.9)
	2023	9 (39.1)
Sex (female)		19 (82.6)
Age	Years	30 (23; 38)
BMI	Kg/m ²	24.5 (16.0; 37.2)
Lung function		
FEV₁	L	3.4 (0.8)
PEF	L/min	519.1 (113)
Differential cell counts		
White blood cells	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	6.1 (1.5)
Granulocytes	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	3.4 (1.3)
Neutrophils	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	3.2 (1.1)
Eosinophils	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	0.1 (0.1)
Lymphocytes	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	1.6 (0.5)
Monocytes	# cells *10 ⁹ /L	0.4 (0.2)

*Abbreviations: IQR = interquartile range; BMI = body mass index; FEV1 = forced expiratory volume in one second; PEF = peak expiratory flow.

exposed to passive smoking either the day before or on the day of the visit (n = 9; 14.1 %).

Fig. 2 and S3 show spaghetti plots of percentage changes of total and differential WBCs over the three timepoints across the measurement sites, per individual. For all WBC subtypes, substantial inter-variability in changes in cell counts could be observed.

3.2. Traffic-related micro- and nanoplastic levels

Table 2 shows the distributions of the four-hour average air pollutant concentrations and weather parameters. Rubber markers showed large variability between measurement days (Table 2). Compared to the park, the synthetic- and natural rubber levels were on average 2.8–4.6 times higher at the stop-and-go location (Fig. S4). A Pearson correlation matrix with the pairwise correlations between rubber markers and other air pollutants is shown in Fig. 3. Rubber markers were highly correlated with each other (r = 0.69 to 0.99). Synthetic rubber markers were highly correlated with traffic-related pollutants BC and Abs (r = 0.71 to 0.76), and brake wear-related elements Fe, Cu, Cr and Mn (>0.61) (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Between- and within-subject variation in monocytes and neutrophils (expressed as percentages), measured at baseline (timepoint = 1), immediately after exposure (timepoint = 2), and the following morning (timepoint = 3). Black lines represent the average changes in cell counts. Please note different scales.

3.3. Associations rubber markers and white blood cell counts

Fig. 4 shows associations between an IQR increase in air pollutants and changes in percentages of whole blood neutrophils and monocytes after six- and 17 h (compared to baseline, main model). The estimates of the other differential WBCs and for the other models, can be found in respectively Table S2 and Figs. S5A – S5C.

Immediately after exposure, small, but consistent positive trends were observed between the rubber markers and multiple leukocyte subtypes, including the granulocytes and neutrophils (3.6 to 5.4 %), and monocytes (7.1 to 9.3 %; Fig. 4, Table S2). Specifically, the natural rubber markers and $\sum(\text{NR} + \text{SBR})$ were significantly associated after FDR correction, with a ~ 8 % increase in monocytes immediately after exposure [NR D-Limonene: 7.1 %; 95 % CI (2.6 to 13.5 %); FDR = 0.042; $\sum(\text{NR} + \text{SBR})$ 9.3 %; 95 % CI (2.6 to 16.3 %); FDR = 0.046]. Similar trends were observed between both SBR markers and monocytes, although no longer significant after FDR correction.

The following morning, an IQR increase in all rubber markers was associated with increased total WBCs (7.4 to 13.4 %), granulocytes (8.3 to 14.0 %), neutrophils (8.3 to 14.0 %), monocytes (9.3 to 17.7 %) and a relatively small increase in lymphocytes (4.4 to 5.2 %; Fig. 4, Table S2). Overall, no associations were observed between benzothiazole and any of the total or differential WBCs. The relative effect estimates for the differential WBCs were 1.7 to 1.9-fold larger for an IQR increase in synthetic rubber, compared to the natural rubber markers, albeit with overall broader confidence intervals. Moreover, no consistent trends were observed between rubber markers and changes in eosinophils (Table S2, Fig. S5C). Additionally, no changes in the estimates were observed for any of the sensitivity analyses (Table S3).

3.4. Associations other air pollutants and white blood cell counts

Immediately after exposure, positive trends were observed between BC, brake-wear-related trace elements (Fe, Cr, Mn), NO₂, and leukocyte subsets, particularly granulocytes, neutrophils, and monocytes. Increases for these markers generally ranged between 5–10 %, comparable to associations with traffic-related MNPs. Moreover, the following morning, more variation was observed between individual air pollutants and the various cell subsets. Associations with Fe, Cr, Cu, and Mn became more consistent across total WBCs, granulocytes, neutrophils, and monocytes, with effect estimates typically ranging from 8 % to 17 %. The most pronounced increases were observed for the monocytes, with IQR increases in BC, Fe, Cr, Cu, Mn, and NO₂ associated with changes of approximately 9 % to 17 % (Fig. 4, Figs. S5A–S5C).

Table 2
Distributions of four-hour average measured air pollutant concentrations and weather during exposure sessions (n = 16).

	Unit	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max	IQR
Rubber markers							
SBR Dimer	ng/m ³	12.6	11.9	7.7	2.9	33.1	8.4
SBR Trimer	ng/m ³	13.7	14.1	8.0	0.7	31.3	10.0
NR Dimer	ng/m ³	9.4	7.9	7.7	1.9	29.1	6.2
NR D-Limonene	ng/m ³	7.8	5.3	7.4	1.6	26.8	4.6
Σ(SBR + NR)	ng/m ³	20.4	17.6	14.4	5.2	59.9	13.1
Benzothiazole	(AU/ISTD) ³ /m ³	1.5	1.0	1.8	0.2	7.7	1.1
Other air pollutants							
PM ₁₀	µg/m ³	26.7	26.5	11.9	11.1	52.6	17.6
BC	µg/m ³	1.2	1.1	0.6	0.3	2.3	0.8
Abs	m ⁻⁵	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.1	2.3	0.8
PNC	pt ⁻³ /cm ³	10.6	10.4	4.7	3.4	20.8	3.5
V	ng/m ³	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.1	2.3	0.8
Cr	ng/m ³	3.8	2.9	3.3	0.4	10.9	3.2
Cu	ng/m ³	39.6	33.1	25.1	6.9	96.9	25.7
As	ng/m ³	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.9	0.2
Mn	ng/m ³	9.5	6.3	7.0	1.2	23.9	8.6
Fe	ng/m ³	732.9	342.7	749.6	84.8	2579.2	1151.5
IP	ng/m ³	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.6	0.1
O ₃ ^a	µg/m ³	69.8	72.7	22.7	16.9	102.4	27.3
NO ₂ ^a	µg/m ³	12.0	9.8	7.8	3.4	31.0	10.9
Weather parameters							
Temperature	°C	20.1	19.7	4.1	14.4	28.5	5.8
Rel. humidity	%	58.5	58.4	16.5	32.0	81.4	22.2
Windspeed	m/s	4.1	3.9	1.2	2.2	7.0	1.3

*Abbreviations: NR = natural rubber; SBR = styrene-butadiene rubber; PM₁₀ = particulate matter < 10 µm; BC = black carbon; Abs = absorbance; PNC = particle number concentration; pt = particles; V = Vanadium; Cr = Chromium; Cu = Copper; As = Arsenic; Mn = Manganese; Fe = Iron; IP = Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene; O₃ = ozone; NO₂ = nitrogen dioxide; IQR = interquartile range; SG = stop-and-go; P = park; HW = highway.

^a from fixed sites close to measurement sites.

Fig. 3. Pearson correlation matrix of rubber markers and other air pollutants measured during exposure sessions (n = 16). *Abbreviations: SBR = styrene-butadiene rubber; SBR Dimer = 3-cyclohexen-1-yl benzene; SBR Trimer = 1-phenyl-3,4-divinyl-, (1R,3trans,4trans)-Cyclohexane; NR = natural rubber; NR Dimer2 = 2,5-dimethyl-3-methylene-1,5-heptadiene; BZT = benzothiazole; PM₁₀ = particulate matter < 10 µm; PNC = particle number concentration; Abs = absorbance; BC = black carbon; Fe = Iron; Cu = Copper; Cr = Chromium; As = Arsenic; Mn = manganese; V = Vanadium; NO₂ = Nitrogen Dioxide; O₃ = Ozone; IP = Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene.

3.5. Associations rubber markers and white blood cell counts using two-pollutant models

After adjustment for other TRAPs, we observed minor changes in effect estimates compared to the single-pollutant models, for

associations between synthetic rubber markers and the various differential WBCs (Figs. 5 and S6). Associations between rubber markers and WBC counts also remained robust when using LASSO mixed-effects regression analysis as an alternative to the two-pollutant regression models. Compared to the other air pollutants, rubber markers produced

Fig. 4. Percentage changes in neutrophil and monocyte counts per interquartile range (IQR) increase in atmospheric pollutant levels, as estimated by the main model. Changes were measured immediately after exposure (panels A: neutrophils; C: monocytes) and the following morning (panels B: neutrophils; D: monocytes), versus baseline (grey dotted line). The models included a random intercept for each subject and were adjusted for temperature, relative humidity, pollen, and time trend. *FDR < 0.05.

Fig. 5. Two-pollutant estimates per interquartile range (IQR) of plastic levels and percentage changes in various subsets of white blood cells measured the following morning (t = 17 h) versus baseline (grey dotted line). Top-to-bottom: A) White blood cells, B) neutrophils, and C) monocytes. The linear mixed models (main model) contained a random intercept per subjects and were adjusted for meteorological conditions, pollen count and an interaction term for year*day.

higher coefficients for total and differential WBCs (Table S4).

3.6. Associations of lung function and symptoms

Consistent with the healthy study population, we observed virtually no increases in symptoms after exposure and logistic regression models did not converge or provide interpretable estimates. The distribution of the symptom reporting immediately after exposure can be found in supplement Fig. S7. Moreover, no associations were observed between any of the pollutants and changes in the pairwise lung function differences (Supplement Fig. S8), e.g. effects estimates per IQR were for FEV1 $\sum(\text{NR} + \text{SBR})$ [−0.02; 95 % CI (−0.06 to 0.02 L); $p = 0.48$]; PEF $\sum(\text{NR} + \text{SBR})$ [−2.05; 95 % CI (−11.33 to 7.42 L/min); $p = 0.68$].

4. Discussion

In a semi-controlled exposure study, four-hour exposure to traffic-related MNPs was associated with 5 to 20 % increased cell counts of total and differential WBCs. More pronounced associations were observed 17 h after exposure. Associations remained consistent after adjusting for other traffic-related pollutants. No associations were observed for changes in lung function or symptoms. This is the first epidemiological study providing evidence for short-term health effects associated with exposure to atmospheric traffic-related MNPs.

Semi-controlled exposure designs have been shown to allow robust assessment of effects of TRAPs. A major advantage of such designs is the known exposure of participants, similar to fully controlled exposure studies, while maintaining real-world (mixed) exposure and conditions. The standardized exercise and four-hour duration resulted in large experimental exposure contrasts, as the increased physical activity during the exposure sessions ensured a higher inhaled dose (Table S5). By maintaining a relatively constant heart rate during cycling across sessions, and focusing on the pairwise differences between baseline and follow-up measurements, we were able to assess changes specifically associated with differences in exposure levels. Moreover, the repeated-measurements design enabled assessing individual-level changes among participants, increasing the power of the study. Furthermore, conducting measurements at similar times of the day minimized the influence of the circadian rhythm on absolute levels of immune markers. Including three distinct traffic-sites allowed for the assessment of associations with traffic-related MNPs, while distinguishing effects relative to other TRAPs.

Previous epidemiologically-relevant studies were mainly observational studies, focusing on associations between non-traffic MNP levels in blood or atherosclerotic plaques and multiple clinically-relevant cardiovascular endpoints (Marfella et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024). Marfella et al. (2024) found increased MNP levels within plaques collected from 304 patients undergoing carotid endarterectomy (Marfella et al., 2024). MNP presence was associated with 4.5-fold increased hazard of myocardial infarction, stroke or death, increased macrophages and cytokine levels. A cross-sectional study performed by Yang et al. (2024) determined whole blood MP levels in patients with chest pain, 92 of whom were diagnosed with acute coronary syndrome (Yang et al., 2024). Adjusting for age, they found positive associations between MPs, vascular complexity, immune markers, and cytokine levels. Supporting these findings, two cross-sectional studies found elevated total MNP levels in blood and thrombus samples correlated with adverse cardiovascular endpoints (Wang et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024). All studies focused on patients and the role of MNP exposure in exacerbating cardiovascular risks and pro-inflammatory effects. Therefore, these studies could have been influenced by reversed causality in which the disease itself changes the accumulation of plastics in the tissue. Moreover, measurements of MNPs in biological tissue remains challenging and questions about their validity have been raised (Xu et al., 2025). Notwithstanding, our findings seem to complement this evidence by demonstrating that traffic-related

MNPs can result in pro-inflammatory responses irrespective of other TRAPs, even within healthy subjects. Increased exposure to traffic-related MNPs might trigger more severe responses within vulnerable populations, as seen in these studies and confirmed by animal studies (Ali et al., 2024).

Only few studies looked at short-term effects of exposure to traffic-related PM (2.5 or 10 μm) on WBC counts, observing highly heterogeneous associations (Kubesch et al., 2015; Steenhof et al., 2014). A cross-over study compared short-term high versus low TRAP exposure levels, combined with and without physical activity, and WBC counts 30 min after exposure (Kubesch et al., 2015). A 37.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in coarse PM was associated with a significant increase in neutrophils (5.7 %), on top of the exercise-induced effect. However, they did not observe monocyte changes, in contrast to our results. In a previous study we found positive associations between TRAP and total WBCs [10.5 %; 95 % CI (7.1 to 14.1)] and neutrophils [31.0 %; 95 % CI (25.1 to 37.2)], but negative associations with monocytes [−15.6 %; 95 % CI (−25.4 to −4.6)] immediately after exposure (Steenhof et al., 2014). Seventeen hours later, neutrophils had returned to baseline, while monocytes remained decreased. In that study, we did not have information on (traffic-related) MNPs.

By employing two-pollutant models, we adjusted for other traffic-related primary pollutants, including BC and various brake wear elements. However, it is noteworthy these pollutants are not exclusively derived from brake wear, but are also incorporated during the synthesis of tyres as vulcanization agents, catalysts, or contaminants from crude oil-derived rubbers (O'Loughlin et al., 2023). Adjusting for these markers in the two-pollutant models could therefore represent an overadjustment for tyre wear. Although, the two-pollutant models did not change the results for tyre wear, the moderate correlations with brake wear-related metals warrant caution as these have been shown to have inflammatory effects.

We found null associations between exposure to any air pollutant and changes in lung function or symptoms. In occupational settings, high exposure to atmospheric MNPs has been linked to decreased respiratory function (Turcotte et al., 2013; Murashov et al., 2021). These cross-sectional studies have been focusing on occupational settings working with textile fabrics, polyvinyl chloride or rubber particles. It could be that we did not see an effect due to the inclusion of only the short-term timepoint immediately after exposure. Nonetheless, a priori it was decided not to include a delayed timepoint based on findings from a previous study. Specifically, Strak et al. (2012) observed immediate, but not delayed, associations between short-term exposure to traffic-related air pollution and reductions in lung function within four- to six-hours post-exposure (Strak et al., 2012).

A major strength of the study included the robust repeated-measures design and pairwise comparisons, enhancing internal validity. Recruitment spanned two years, ultimately including 23 participants. While the sample size limited sex- or ethnicity-stratified analyses, the three deliberately selected measurement sites helped account for other traffic-related air pollutants. Multicollinearity concerns were partly addressed using various statistical methods known to perform better with highly correlated predictors. Consistent findings from multi-pollutant exposure models supported the robustness of results. Nonetheless, we cannot exclude that the effects we observed for the rubber markers were attributable to or biased by the highly correlated pollutants. We also did not include direct measurements of PM_{2.5}. Based on previous studies, we expected the contribution of traffic-related MNPs to PM_{2.5} to be limited (Panko et al., 2019; Lenssen et al., 2025). A previous study by Strak et al. (2011), conducted in comparable traffic settings, found a strong correlation between PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} levels, suggesting that in such environments, PM_{2.5} can be reasonably approximated by PM₁₀ (Strak et al., 2011). Nonetheless, the absence of PM_{2.5} measurements constrained our ability to fully disentangle the specific contribution of traffic-related MNPs across size fractions. Additionally, we used pollen data from a monitoring site located ~50 km from the study area. While this was the

closest available data source, it introduces uncertainty in representing local pollen concentrations. We were also unable to measure NO₂ and O₃ on-site and instead used nearby comparable fixed network sites, limiting our ability to adjust for these air pollutants. However, sites at a short distance to each other share similar meteorological conditions, resulting in comparable temporal trends. In support of this, a previous study has shown moderate to high correlations between fixed-site monitors located within short distances and with similar micro-environments, such as areas with comparable traffic intensity or surrounding green spaces (Sajani et al., 2004).

Another limitation was not including the delayed assessment of lung function and respiratory symptoms the following morning. In addition, the instrument we used for lung function testing did not measure forced vital capacity or maximal mid-expiratory flow. We can therefore not exclude that these parameters were affected. A limitation was the lack of full blinding, which may have introduced bias in the self-reported symptoms or lung function measures. However, participants were only aware of the exact site after baseline measurements were collected. Besides, most outcome and exposure measures were objective and unlikely to be much affected by detection bias. Exposure misclassification was mitigated by selecting sites at approximately equal distances from the research facility. An assessment of PNC levels during transport confirmed the absence of consistent differences between the routes to the various exposure sites (Table S5).

In summary, exposure to traffic-related MNPs was associated with an increase in monocytes immediately after exposure, and with a sustained and increased total WBCs, neutrophils (granulocytes) and especially monocytes the following morning. Associations were mostly independent of other traffic-related combustion-, and brake wear-related air pollutants. These associations were indicative of a pro-inflammatory effect due to short-term exposure to traffic-related MNPs.

Details on ethical approval

The study protocol (#22/515) was approved by the local medical ethics review committee (NedMec, Utrecht, The Netherlands). Participants signed written informed consent forms.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Esther S. Lenssen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gerard Hoek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Lorenzo Scibetta:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Tim L.P. Skrabanja:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Laura Caiazzo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Nienke Vriesekoop:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Marja Lamoree:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Roel Vermeulen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Raymond H.H. Pieters:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109732>.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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